

Factors Influencing Performance and Satisfaction in Learning Business Analytics among Sri Lankan Undergraduates

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Abstract

Business Analytics (BA) has become a vital area within higher education as organizations increasingly depend on data-driven decision-making processes. Previous research indicates that students' academic performance and satisfaction in BA programs are influenced by multiple interconnected factors, including course design, personal motivation, perceived career relevance, and self-efficacy. However, many existing studies tend to examine these factors separately, without fully exploring how they collectively shape the overall learning experience. In developing contexts such as Sri Lanka, concerns persist regarding whether graduates are adequately prepared to apply analytical knowledge in professional settings. In response, this study investigates the key factors affecting undergraduate students' academic performance and satisfaction in learning Business Analytics, with particular attention to the roles of self-efficacy, personal interest, perceived career relevance, and perceived effectiveness of course structure, as well as their impact on learning effort. A quantitative, cross-sectional research design was employed, using a structured online questionnaire administered to 120 undergraduates from UGC-approved universities in the Western Province of Sri Lanka. The conceptual framework was developed by integrating constructs from established technology adoption and motivation theories. Data was analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling through SmartPLS software. The findings reveal that self-efficacy significantly strengthens learning effort, which in turn positively affects academic performance. Perceived course structure effectiveness also demonstrates a strong direct influence on both performance and satisfaction. In contrast, personal interest and perceived career relevance do not show a significant effect on learning effort, and learning effort does not significantly predict student satisfaction. These results emphasize the critical importance of well-structured course design and learner confidence in enhancing educational outcomes, while acknowledging limitations related to the cross-sectional design and geographically limited sample.

Keywords: *Business Analytics Education, Learning Effort, Academic Performance, Satisfaction, Sri Lankan Undergraduates*